

Ethiopia Multi-Actor Community Meeting (MAC) and Regional Stakeholders Meeting (RSM) Insight: The Key Takeaway Messages and Recommendations

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Group photo: Participants of the 4th GA meeting held at Inter Luxury Hotel, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia

The Strategic Insights

The Ethiopian MAC meeting held in September 2025 reaffirmed that Push-Pull Technology (PPT) remains among the cornerstones and key strategies towards agroecological intensification, but its long-term impact depends on how effectively it is embedded within institutional, policy, and partnership frameworks beyond the life of the UPSCALE project that will be coming to an end in April 2026. While notable progress has been achieved, the discussions among the stakeholders revealed that sustainability, adoption, adaptation, and scaling remain the critical frontiers in all the East African countries. All the partners should be involved in the planning and execution process for acceptability and ownership of the socio-economic outcomes.

Take-away Messages

The key message from the MAC and RSM meetings was the indispensable role of MACs. Participants strongly agreed that MACs should not end with the project but instead continue as permanent platforms for coordination, learning, and co-creation. MACs provide the institutional glue that brings together farmers, researchers, policymakers, private sector actors, and other development partners. Without their continuity, many of the gains achieved risk stagnation or reversal of all the efforts made.

The meeting underscored that PPT is technically sound, economically viable, and environmentally beneficial. Evidence from the field shows that PPT improves yields, reduces aflatoxin contamination in maize and other cereal crops, and increases farm profitability. Importantly, while initial investment costs may appear high, these costs decline over time, whereas benefits accumulate as farms stabilize and productivity improves. This long-term benefit profile positions PPT as a strategic investment rather than a short-term intervention.

However, adoption patterns revealed a critical insight. Push-Pull Technology adoption is neither linear nor spontaneous. Uptake of PPT by farmers varies significantly by location, institutional support, and intensity of engagement. Adoption must therefore be actively facilitated, requiring sustained extension, policy support, and multi-actor engagement. Women and elderly farmers were observed to adopt PPT more readily, suggesting that gender and social dynamics should be intentionally leveraged in future scaling strategies.

Despite intensive promotion efforts, adoption levels remain lower than expected. This highlights that promotion alone is insufficient. Farmers face unresolved constraints, including access to planting materials, labor demands, limited mechanisation options, and unclear profitability comparisons with alternative systems. The meeting emphasized the need for farmer-centred, demand-driven research that responds directly to these constraints.

Another strong message was that PPT should not be viewed as a stand-alone technology. Participants recognized the importance of integrating PPT with complementary crops and innovations. Successful integration with crops such as kales, tomatoes, green grams, and pigeon pea demonstrates that PPT can evolve into a flexible farming system, rather than a rigid package. Exploring synergies with other agroecological practices will be essential for broadening its appeal and relevance.

Policy engagement emerged as both a gap and an opportunity. The functionality and influence of MACs depend heavily on active participation by policymakers. Without supportive policies, markets for agroecology products remain weak, and incentives for adoption remain limited. Furthermore, the roles of some MAC structures, particularly FA MACs, remain insufficiently defined, reducing their effectiveness.

Finally, the meeting highlighted the need for stronger partnerships and innovative scaling pathways. Scaling PPT to commercial farmers with more than two acres requires tailored approaches, including mechanisation, input supply systems, and private sector engagement. Existing materials and knowledge can support this transition, but partnerships particularly with agri-tech developers and machinery designers are essential.

Recommendations

Building on these insights, the meeting proposed that;

The UPSCALE partners should ensure Continuity of MACs beyond the Project.

MACs should be retained as associate partners within a broader agroecology alliance rather than remaining project-bound entities.

Regular coordination mechanisms such as webinars, online meetings, and joint proposal development should be institutionalised to sustain momentum.

Mainstream PPT through context-specific approaches, PPT scaling should be adapted to local agroecological and socio-economic contexts.

Develop clear and practical PPT guidelines for different farming systems, including both small-scale and commercial operations. For instance, have guidelines on how to roll out PPT to commercial farmers who have more than 2 acres through programs such as the provision of farm inputs and planting materials, and a clear plan on how to establish partnerships for productive ideas and implementation.

Strengthen research for adoption and impact. Future research should prioritise;

1. Comparative profitability analysis of PPT versus alternative systems
2. Farmer-identified constraints and labour dynamics
3. Synergies between PPT and complementary technologies

Deepen policy engagement and advocacy. The governments should be engaged at local, national, and regional levels to create a conducive policy environment for agroecology.

PPT and ecological intensification should be embedded in education curricula, extension systems, and agricultural development strategies.

Expand partnerships for innovation and scaling, where new partners, including agri-tech developers, machinery manufacturers, and private investors, should be engaged to co-create scalable solutions, such as mechanised planting and harvesting (e.g., desmodium seed harvesting technologies).

Invest in capacity building and knowledge dissemination through schools, roadshows, stakeholder workshops, and digital platforms as entry points for creating awareness and learning. Youth entrepreneurship and agroecology value chains should be actively promoted.

Conclusion

The overarching message from the Ethiopia MAC and RSM meetings was that PPT works, MACs matter, and continuity is non-negotiable. The future of agroecological intensification in East Africa lies not in isolated projects, but in enduring platforms, inclusive partnerships, and policies that enable farmers to adopt, adapt, and benefit sustainably from proven innovations like Push-Pull Technology.

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